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STUDY OF THE ATTITUDE OF PEOPLE TOWARDS RECYCLING ACTIVITY IN SOUTH CANARA DISTRICT

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Abstract

India is a very big country with a total area of 3,287,590 km² and 2,973,193 km² by Land. It has a population of 1.237 billion, as per May 2014 (17.4% of total world population) right next to China, and soon to take over it by 2025. Looking at India's population growth, this is at 1.76% per annum during 2001–2011. It would not be wrong to say that the consumption patter is likely to boom. So will the waste after it has been consumed. Given all these facts, India might face situation in recycling these materials.

The major role in this scenario is that of household to whom most of the consumption is associated with. This survey seeks to collect information about what people think about the act of recycling and whether they are undertaking any kinds of household recycling. It should be noted that this survey was conducted on the population size of 100 respondents. These respondents were mainly from parts of South Canara district.

Key words: Recycling, Environment, Health, Waste Management

Introduction:

Recycling is the process of recovering and reusing waste products—from household use, manufacturing, agriculture, and business—and thereby reducing their burden on the environment. During World War I and World War II, shortages of essential materials led to collection drives for silk, rubber, and other commodities. In recent years the environmental benefits of recycling have become a major component of waste management programs.

For the environmentally conscious citizens, disposing off non-biodegradable objects like used plastic bottles, cups or paper has become a major concern. This research is directed to see how the households are concerned about disposing these non-biodegradable objects and how they are doing it.

Background of Study:

The study was conducted with the sole intention to analyse the recycling pattern of household in South Canara. The study gives a detailed way of mode, frequency of recycling in Organic and non-organic wastes and the method they go forth recycling them. It also gives a detailed perception of respondents about the authority responsibility and duty in recycling activity. The research in conducted in three levels; Living Pattern, Opinion about recycling and activities respondents are involved in. This level of research gives a clear picture about respondents' attitude, belief and perception towards recycling. Research also covers aspects related to environmental friendly materials and their acceptance.

Statement of Problem:

There are many environmental issues in India. Air pollution, water pollution, garbage, and these are all challenges for India. The situation was worse between 1947 through 1995. According to data collection and environment assessment studies of World Bank experts, between 1995 through 2010, India has made one of the fastest progresses in the world, in addressing its environmental issues and improving its environmental quality. Still, India has a long way to go to reach environmental quality similar to those enjoyed in developed economies. Pollution remains a major challenge and opportunity for India. Environmental issues are one of the primary causes of disease, health issues and long term livelihood impact for India. Thus, these factors gave rise to our research.

Hypothesis:

- Our Hypothesis is that Correlation between Dustbins in locality and its management is not significant;
- Our second hypothesis is that, Respondents do not believe household recycling to be important;
- It should be noted that the research is undertaken in South Canara with a sample size of 100 respondents.

Objective of Study:

This research is directed to seek;

- To see whether households are involved in recycling of these materials or are intended to do so;
- Process or Mode they follow for recycling;
- Whether recycling has provided them with source of funds;
- To understand respondents attitude towards recycling activity;
- To see respondents attitude about implications on Environment and Health if recycling is not undertaken;
- Understanding respondents' opinion about quality of recycled materials and their level of acceptance towards it;
- To see the feasibility of carrying out recycling;
- Respondent's perception towards responsibility and duty of authority in initiating the recycling process.

Need of the study:

Recycling is an important factor in conserving natural resources and greatly contributes towards improving the environment. Recycling in and around the home can be easy when you know how. By thinking carefully about what products you buy at the supermarket and how to recycle them is the first step towards efficient recycling.

Many materials can be recycled, such as paper, plastic, metal and glass. Other items such as furniture, electronic equipment, building material and vehicles can also be recycled but many people don't often think to do so. When shopping at the supermarket, buy products that can be recycled easily such as glass jars and tin cans. By recycling garden products and planting trees, you can help improve the environment in your back garden.

Composting is a process where waste degrades into compost, which can then be used in your garden to help it grow. It is an excellent way to recycle garden and kitchen waste such as plant trimmings and leftover food.

Scope of the study:

Whatever we consume generates a lot of garbage and waste. Discarding of products adds to the clutter of the dustbins. But what happens with this garbage is a thought less of. Cities worldwide are having huge loads of garbage. Indian cities are no better. Before dumping the garbage in a landfill it should be treated for safe disposal and recycled for various use. The municipalities are inefficient and unsuccessful in managing the garbage in cities.

The garbage generated from various sources consists of different types of waste. The process of recycling is different for different type of material found in the waste pile. A typical system of solid

waste management includes segregation, reuse, and recycling at the household level, waste collection and transport to a transfer station or community bin, street sweeping and cleansing of public places, management of the transfer station or community bin, secondary collection and transport to the waste disposal site & waste disposal in landfills. Disposal methods include incineration, plasma gasification, landfill and recycling. Recycled garbage is used in composting, producing energy like refuse derived fuel, making animal food, reusing the material in art and craft, same industry, as a raw material in another industry.

Methodology:

In any research the method of conducting the whole process is more important than the output we get. The survey has been conducted in the most systematic manner possible. Data Collection has been done in two forms; First, Primary data which have responses of 100 respondents, Second, Secondary data which is second hand information from sources such as Research Articles, Magazines, Newspapers, etc.

In an of the research sample size plays a greater role to determine the output of any research. In this study the sample sizes have been a total of 100 people who have been selected randomly, of which 38 were female and 62 were male respondents.

Data Analysis is a major part in any research it helps us to determine the meaning of the data collected and will also help us to interpret them.

Literature Review:

"Industrialization has given rise to a lot of casual consumption. Not much thought is given to reusing or recycling these materials". **Payal Gwalani, TNN | Aug 28, 2013**

Waste is a material that no longer serves a purpose and so is thrown away. In some cases what one person discards may be re-used by somebody else. All wastes are particularly hazardous: If not carefully disposed of, it will have an impact on the environment, whether it is unsightly litter in urban streets or contaminated air, soil or water. But what is equally important about waste is that it is recyclable. For example, if all human, animal and solid wastes are recycled back to soil, then we do not need inorganic fertilizers to maintain the high yields of crops. Today India produces 180 million tonnes of food grains and consumes 13 million tonnes of inorganic fertilizers at a huge cost. Therefore, time has come when we have to look at the waste not merely as an environment polluter but a recyclable material of great potential and energy saver.

The problem in these cities is how to dispose such large mass of solid waste daily and this poses a massive and expensive problem to the authorities. The composition of average domestic dustbin can be broken down as follows:

- 10% Glass
- 30% Paper/Cardboard
- 9% Metals
- 3% Textiles
- 4% Plastics
- 23% Vegetable Waste
- 21% Dust, Cinders, Miscellaneous

If proper measures are not taken to dispose this material it can cause health disorder.

So disposing them is very important. Here are the levels of waste disposal:

(a) Control of Waste at Source:

The volume of solid waste will be greatly reduced if conscious people compost and utilise the daily organic waste in their kitchen-garden as manure.

(b) Segregation of Waste at Source:

If conscious people do not use the organic waste in their kitchen-garden, the least they can do is to segregate the inorganic waste i.e. fused bulbs, blades, and razors, old shoes, tooth paste tubes, glass wares, empty bottles etc. at source Municipalities should create a bank or a dumping point where inorganic waste can be sent by a simple and effective collection system. For example, a municipal official can visit each street after every fortnight to collect such wastes from each house. In Western

countries waste banks have been formed where people can sell empty glass bottles or deposit other inorganic wastes. Fortunately, in our country, a lot of inorganic waste is already being recycled.

(c) Collection and Transportation:

The Municipality will have to design a simple and effective system of waste collection for each street. At this stage, the local eco- club, sanitation committees can be very effective through mutual cooperation and motivation. The primary collection can be through wheel-barrow system. This waste can be dumped at a transit dump site. The municipal trucks can pick up this waste from these transit dump sites and transport to the final disposal site.

(d) The Final Disposal:

The final disposal site can be one or more depending upon the size of the city. But one disposal site in each direction of the city will certainly reduce the cost of transportation.

Data Analysis and Interpretation:

1. Respondent Profile:

Below respondents profile regarding the gender group of respondents participated in the survey, place of their residence, number of family members have been given.

Table 1.1: Respondents for the survey

Gender	Frequency	Per cent
Male	62	62.0
Female	38	38.0
Total	100	100.0

Table 1.2: Place of Residence

Place of Residence	Frequency	Per cent
Apartment	11	11.0
Independent House	75	75.0
Joint Family	14	14.0
Total	100	100.0

Table 1.3: Numbers of Family Members

Number	Frequency	Per cent
0-3	10	10.0
4-6	80	80.0
7-9	4	4.0
10-Above	2	2.0
missing	4	4.0
Total	100	100.0

Respondent Profile: About 62 per cent of the respondents to the survey are Male and 38 per cent are Female [Table 1.1].

100 respondents who were interviewed, 10 per cent belong to 0-3 size of family structure, a major chunk of the respondents belong to 4-6 size of family structure about 80 per cent, 4 per cent to 7-9 size of family structure, 2 per cent to 10-above and about 4 per cent of the respondents haven't disclosed their family size [Table 1.3].

Place of residence is an important factor determining the living pattern of individual. 11 per cent of the Individual resided in Apartments, 75 per cent of the population resided in Independent House, and 14 per cent from joint families.

2. Dustbin in respondents house:

Below the dustbin in respondents house is interpreted.

Table 2.1: Dustbin in house

	Frequency	Per cent
Yes	87	87.0
No	9	9.0
missing	4	4.0
Total	100	100.0

Interpretation: From the data collected 87 per cent of the respondents have dustbins in their house where as 9 per cent don't and 4 per cent people have not replied to have or not. It can clearly be interpreted that about 87 per cent of the respondents who maintain dustbin accumulate waste which might be a recyclable.

3. Respondents knowledge about recycling process:

Below Respondents knowledge about recycling process in interpreted.

	Frequency	Per cent
Yes	66	66.0
No	34	34.0
Total	100	100.0

Interpretation: Out of 100 respondents interviewed 34 per cent of them have no knowledge about recycling process. 66 per cent people are aware about recycling process. It can be interpreted that 34 per cent people of the population have to be educated regarding the recycling process if the problem related to recycling need to solve.

4. Household Recycling as a source of fund for respondents

Below the respondents funds received through recycling is mentioned.

	Frequency	Per cent
Missing	4	4.0
Always	5	5.0
Frequently	34	34.0
Occasionally	25	25.0
Never	19	19.0
not applicable	13	13.0
Total	100	100.0

Interpretation: Recycling activity has been provided with source of fund. The amount of which might not be very high. According to data collected it is clear that only 5 per cent of the respondents have always gained source of fund through recycling, 34 per cent of whom have gained on frequent intervals, 25 per cent have occasionally gained from recycling, 19 per cent have never gained any source of fund through recycling, 13 per cent of the population says gaining source of fund is not applicable to them. 4 per cent of the remaining population have not disclosed their status of funds from recycling.

5. Hindrances faced by respondents while undertaking recycling activity:

Below table shows respondents treating recycling as a hard Job.

	Frequency	Per cent
Missing	1	1.0
strongly agree	10	10.0
Agree	44	44.0
nor agree nor disagree	31	31.0
Disagree	12	12.0
strongly disagree	2	2.0
Total	100	100.0

Interpretation: One of the main elements of the research is respondent perception towards recycling activity. It was found out that 10 per cent of the respondents strongly agreed recycling to be hard job, while 44 per cent of the respondents agreed, 31 per cent neither agreed or disagreed, and while 12 per cent disagreed and 2 per cent strongly disagreed.

Table 5.1: Difficulty in carrying out recycling

Difficulty in household recycling is interpreted below.

	Frequency	Per cent
Missing	5	5.0
There is insufficient recycle bins in locality	23	23.0
Recycling Facilities are set up in inconvenient Places	39	39.0
Recycle bins not cleared regularly	29	29.0
Others	4	4.0
Total	100	100.0

Interpretation: In the interpretation of Table 5.1 it is clear as to respondent perception of recycling being a hard job. But it does not give us a clear idea as to, why respondents think so? Table 5.2 gives a clear reason as to why respondents think recycling as difficult. About 39 per cent respondents' claim it is due to facilities located in inconvenient place, 23 per cent claim it is the insufficient recycle bins in locality, while 29 per cent people claim it to be due to the recycle bins not cleared on regular intervals, 4 per cent believe it to be other factors such as irregularity and incompetency of authorities, 5 per cent respondents preferred not to answer.

6. Authority vs. Recycling:

Authorities and their responsibility towards recycling in explained below.

Table 6.1: Authorities responsibility for collection and disposal of recyclable materials.

	Frequency	Per cent
strongly agree	26	26.0
Agree	36	36.0
nor agree nor disagree	29	29.0
Disagree	8	8.0
strongly disagree	1	1.0
Total	100	100.0

Interpretation: During the study it was found out that respondents believed that responsibility of authorities in collection and disposal of recyclable materials played a vital role. Data depicts 26 per cent and 36 per cent respondents strongly agree, agree respectively. 29 per cent neither agree nor disagree. 8 per cent disagrees, 1 per cent strongly disagrees.

Factor of responsibility of authorities can be well interpreted with the help of correlation between dustbins in locality and their management by authorities. In this case they are highly correlated the significance level is lesser than 0.05. It proves that the Dustbins in locality and their management are not properly undertaken as mentioned.

Table 6.2: Correlation between Dustbins in locality and their management

		Dustin Management	Dustbins in Locality
Dustin Management	Pearson Correlation	1	-.253*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.011
	N	100	100
Dustbins in Locality	Pearson Correlation	-.253*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.011	
	N	100	100

**. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).*

7. Respondents participation in household recycling:

Respondents participation in household recycling is mentioned below, with concerned responses.

Table 7.1: Respondents interest to participate in recycling

	Frequency	Per cent
strongly agree	27	27.0
Agree	48	48.0
nor agree nor disagree	19	19.0
Disagree	4	4.0
strongly disagree	2	2.0
Total	100	100.0

Interpretation: There was a greater finding in this case where, 48 per cent and 27 per cent respondents wish to participate in the household recycling activity. 19 per cent neither agree nor disagree. 6 per cent respondents would not wish to participate in recycling activity.

Table 7.2 Factors that would influence encouragement in household recycling

Factors that would influence encouragement of households in recycling is mentioned here.

	Frequency	Per cent
sufficient recycle bins in locality	27	27.0
placing recycle bins in convenient places	39	39.0
regular collection and dispose of recyclable materials	33	33.0
other	1	1.0
Total	100	100.0

Interpretation: In our study we found out, the factors that would encourage respondents to undertake recycling activity. 27 per cent pointed out sufficient recycle bins in locality would encourage them to participate in recycling. While 39 per cent claimed it to be recycle bins to be in convenient places, 33 per cent believed regular collection and dispose of materials by authorities would encourage.

8. Perception towards recycled products:

Perception towards recycled products is a vital aspect of our study it has been interpreted below.

Table 8.1: Prefer ability and durability of recycled materials.

	Frequency	Per cent
strongly agree	18	18.0
Agree	48	48.0
nor agree nor disagree	32	32.0
Disagree	2	2.0
Total	100	100.0

Interpretation: 48 per cent respondents agree that the recycled materials are durable and would prefer buying them. Meanwhile 32 per cent neither agree nor disagree, 2 per cent disagree.

Table 8.2: Quality of Recycled materials

Quality of the recycled materials and its influence on respondents is explained below.

	Frequency	Per cent
Highly Satisfied	9	9.0
Satisfied	43	43.0
Nor Satisfied Nor Unsatisfied	27	27.0
Unsatisfied	16	16.0
Highly Unsatisfied	5	5.0
Total	100	100.0

Interpretation: While enquiring about the satisfaction level relating to quality of recycled products, 43 per cent were satisfied, 27 per cent were neither satisfied nor dissatisfied, and 16 per cent were unsatisfied regarding quality of recycled products.

Table 8.3: Acceptance towards Environmental Friendly and Low Cost materials

Below is the interpretation of respondents acceptance towards environmental friendly and low cost materials.

	Frequency	Per cent
Always	50	50.0
Sometimes	44	44.0
Never	6	6.0
Total	100	100.0

Interpretation: We made a study if respondents would be willing to accept a product if it is environmental friendly and is made totally out of recycled material. 50 per cent and 44 per cent respondents claim to use them always while others prefer to use them sometimes. 6 per cent would never prefer to accept such product.

9. Recycling Vs. Environment, Health, Suitability:

It is essential to know the respondents perception effects on Environment, health caused from not recycling.

Table 9.1(a): Recycling Keeps surrounding clean

	Frequency	Per cent
strongly agree	55	55.0
Agree	31	31.0
nor agree nor disagree	11	11.0
disagree	2	2.0
strongly disagree	1	1.0
Total	100	100.0

Interpretation: Respondents were asked if recycling of materials instead of throwing them everywhere would keep the surroundings clean. Majority of the sample population agreed about 55 per cent strongly agreed, 31 per cent agreed. 11 per cent neither agree nor disagree, 2 per cent disagreed, and 1 per cent of whom strongly disagreed.

Table 9.1(b): Recycled Materials and Health risks

	Frequency	Per cent
strongly agree	20	20.0
Agree	17	17.0
nor agree nor disagree	38	38.0
Disagree	20	20.0
strongly disagree	5	5.0
Total	100	100.0

Interpretation: Health issue caused due to materials not being recycled is a major issue. When asked, 20 per cent respondents strongly agreed with the fact that not recycling the waste would cause health related problem, while 17 per cent agreed, 38 per cent neither agreed nor disagreed, 20 per cent disagreed, 5 per cent strongly disagreed.

Table 9.2: Recycling Suitability to India

Respondents thought towards household recycling being suitable for country like India, is mentioned below.

	Frequency	Per cent
strongly agree	29	29.0
Agree	49	49.0
nor agree nor disagree	15	15.0
disagree	5	5.0
strongly disagree	2	2.0
Total	100	100.0

Interpretation: Knowing people perception regarding household recycling and its suitability to country like India is vital. While respondents were interviewed, 49 per cent agreed, 15 per cent neither agreed nor disagreed, 2 per cent strongly disagreed.

10. Better Substitutes for Recycling

Substitutes for recycling is mentioned below.

Table 10.1: Burying or Burning Better Substitute for recycling

	Frequency	Per cent
strongly agree	17	17.0
agree	36	36.0
nor agree nor disagree	30	30.0
disagree	9	9.0
strongly disagree	8	8.0
Total	100	100.0

Interpretation: Burying and burning has been a substitute for recycling from a long time. When asked so, 36 per cent agreed it to be better substitute. While, 30 per cent neither agreed nor disagreed and 9 per cent disagreed.

11. Respondents perception regarding importance of recycling

Table 11.1: Respondents Perception regarding importance of recycling

Total N	100
Test Statistic	90.000
Degrees of Freedom	3
Asymptotic Sig. (2-sided test)	.000

1. There are 0 cells (0%) with expected values less than 5. The minimum expected value is 25.

Interpretation

Hypothesis Test Summary

	Null Hypothesis	Test	Sig.	Decision
1	The categories of Importance of recycling occur with equal probabilities.	One-Sample Chi-Square Test	.000	Reject the null hypothesis.

Asymptotic significances are displayed. The significance level is .05.

12. Items recycled by the respondents according to its frequency

12.1: Frequency of Newspaper Recycling and Frequency Recycling

	Frequency of news paper recycling	Frequency of magazine recycling	Frequency of plastic bag recycling	Frequency of paper bag recycling	Frequency of Organic Waste Recycling
Always	50	32	23	21	28
Frequently	33	34	38	41	32
Occasionally	15	30	24	28	23
Never	2	4	9	7	10
Unanswered	-	-	4	3	7
Total	100	100	100	100	100

The Above data is pertaining to the frequency in which the respondents are involved in recycling activity.

13. Items recycled by respondents according to the mode they follow to recycle them

The above tables clearly gives a picture about the mode followed by respondents to recycle various recyclable materials.

	mode of news paper recycling	mode of magazine recycling	mode of plastic bag recycling	mode of paper bag recycling	mode of organic wate recycling
	Frequency	Frequency	Frequency	Frequency	Frequency
Recycle collectors	51	54	43	40	34
Self recycling	31	33	25	27	29
Unanswered	12	13	32	33	37
Total	100	100	100	100	100

Findings and Conclusion:

This study has given really vital information regarding household recycling.

- **Recycling of house hold materials:** It was found out that out of 100 respondents majority of the respondents had good understanding about household recycling ,they were also involved in recycling of various house hold materials.
- **Recycling as the source of fund:** House hold recycling has provided source of fund, although the amount is not very high recycling has provided some funds to yhe respondents.
- **Respondance perception towards recycling:** During the study it was found out that respondents believed that responsibility of authorities in collection and disposal of recyclable materials played a vital role . There is huge number of population that believes that authorities are responsible in the Recycling Process.
- **Respondents Interest to participate in recycling activity:** There was a greater finding in this case where respondents wish to participate in the household recycling activity. It can be easily concluded that, the interested population should be encouraged in order to promote recycling, such that it will reach huge chunks of population.
- **Recycling and its suitability in India:** Knowing people perception regarding household recycling and its suitability to country like India is vital. While respondents were interviewed, 49 per cent agreed. It shows a considerable improvement in people’s thinking. Thus, it can be concluded people are getting aware about recycling process and are clear as to its prominence in country like India.

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